

Impact of a multimodal care strategy on the prevention of peripheral venous catheter–related phlebitis: findings from the Flebitis Zero Project

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ABSTRACT

Background: Peripheral venous catheters are ubiquitous in hospitals, yet phlebitis remains common despite single-measure prevention. Robust long-term evidence on whether comprehensive bundles sustainably reduce phlebitis is limited. The objective was to determine whether a 5-element bundle (Flebitis Zero) reduces peripheral venous catheters -related phlebitis and whether increasing adherence confers incremental benefit.

Methods: A quasi-experimental pre-post study was conducted in 93 Spanish hospitals (2017-2024). All peripheral venous catheters placed in adult medical and surgical wards during 15 consecutive days each year were prospectively audited (78,691 PVC in 53,121 patients). Daily data included bundle adherence (nine indicators) and phlebitis (Maddox score ≥ 2 points). Frequencies, relative risks (RR) with 95% confidence intervals and Mantel-Haenszel χ^2 tests for linear trend were calculated (Stata 15; $p < 0.05$).

Results: Phlebitis incidence declined from 12.1% at baseline to 9.9% after eight years (18% relative reduction). Seven of nine indicators improved by 5-15 percentage points (pp), most notably sterile polyurethane dressing (+9.6 pp), hand hygiene (+7 pp) and secure fixation away from the insertion site (+5.7 pp). A clear dose-response emerged: implementing ≥ 3 measures conferred an additional 17-25% risk reduction versus ≤ 2 measures, and fulfilling the four audited actions achieved up to 77% lower risk (RR 0.23, 95% CI 0.11-0.49; trend χ^2 to 67.4, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: Incremental compliance with the Flebitis Zero bundle sustainably decreases peripheral venous catheters -related phlebitis. Achieving at least three measures should be the minimum quality target, while full bundle adoption offers

maximal protection. These multicenter data provide robust evidence to support embedding comprehensive peripheral venous catheters care bundles in routine hospital practice.

Key words: Phlebitis/prevention & control; Catheterization, Peripheral/adverse effects; Patient Care Bundles; Infection Control; Incidence; Quasi-Experimental Studies.

Key Messages

What is already known on this topic? Previous studies have established that healthcare bundles are effective for preventing central line-associated bloodstream infections. However, the effectiveness of a multimodal care bundle specifically designed and implemented for the prevention of phlebitis associated with peripheral venous catheters (PVCs) across multiple hospital units was not well-documented. This study was needed to test the real-world impact of the ‘Flebitis Zero’ bundle.

What this study adds? The implementation of the Flebitis Zero bundle was associated with a significant, sustained, and progressive reduction in the relative risk (RR) of phlebitis over an eight-year period (2017-2024). Specifically, adherence to four of the bundle’s measures led to the largest risk reduction, confirming a dose-response relationship between bundle compliance and lower phlebitis rates.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy? These findings provide a strong empirical basis to inform clinical guidelines and support wider implementation in hospital settings, enhancing patient safety regarding peripheral venous catheters.

Introduction

Phlebitis, a common complication of peripheral venous catheter (PVC) use, has a highly variable incidence, with rates typically ranging between 1% and 31% of hospitalised patients, depending on diagnostic criteria, population, and clinical practices¹⁻⁴. Despite routine PVC use for intravenous therapy⁵, phlebitis significantly impacts care quality and increases healthcare costs^{2,6-8}. Preventive strategies—such as using polyurethane catheters⁹, aseptic techniques^{5,10-12}, and antiseptics like 2% chlorhexidine^{5,10,12}, have shown benefits, yet incidence remains high¹³. Untreated phlebitis can lead to severe infections and systemic complications^{2,6,7}, burdening healthcare systems¹⁴. Although multimodal interventions have reduced complications¹⁵⁻¹⁹, limitations in study design and evidence consistency persist. The aim of this study was to determine the effectiveness of a high-evidence care bundle in lowering short peripheral venous catheter-related phlebitis rates in an eight-year multicenter cohort of hospitalised patients, analysing outcomes according to adherence to each individual measure and to their various combinations.

Methods

Study design, setting, and population

We performed a quasi-experimental pre-/post-intervention study with annual prospective cohort follow-up in 93 Spanish hospitals participating in the Flebitis Zero project between 2017 and 2024²⁰. Surveillance encompassed 78,691 short peripheral venous catheters inserted in 53,121 patients, with data collected during a 15-day observation period each year. Each hospital contributed at least one medical and one surgical ward. Inclusion criteria were: (i) age \geq 18 years; (ii) receipt of intravenous pharmacological therapy through the target PVC at any point during the hospital stay; and (iii) provision of informed consent. Exclusion criteria were: (i) PVCs inserted in emergency departments, pediatrics, operating theatres, or recovery units; (ii) PVCs

inserted on wards other than the one in which the patient was located at the time of assessment; and (iii) PVCs placed before the start date of the study.

The nurses responsible for cannulating each PVC informed the patient or their legal representative about the study and obtained verbal consent for participation.

Flebitis Zero bundle

The standardized Flebitis Zero intervention comprises five evidence-based recommendations (Table 1)^{20,21}:

- Appropriate catheter selection (IB).
- Hand hygiene (IA)
- Use of chlorhexidine for skin preparation during both insertion and maintenance of the PVC (IA)
- Aseptic catheter maintenance (IB)
- Prompt removal of unnecessary PVCs (IB)

Implementation of the proposed measures was undertaken through a 30-hour training program delivered to all involved professionals (nurses and physicians) at the participating hospitals. The curriculum focused on the indication, insertion, and maintenance of vascular access in accordance with the bundle established in the project.

The program comprised foundational content delivered online, supplemented by support from designated coordinators at each hospital. Educational resources, such as instructional videos, were provided, and face-to-face sessions and hands-on workshops were organised to reinforce the material and ensure correct implementation of the measures.

Study variables and data collection

The primary outcome was the presence or absence of phlebitis in the vein bearing the PVC. Phlebitis was assessed using the Jackson Infusion Phlebitis Visual Scale, derived from the Maddox scale²². The scale comprises six grades of phlebitis:

- Grade 0: no pain, erythema, swelling, or palpable cord.
- Grade 1: pain without erythema, inflammation, or palpable cord at the puncture site.
- Grade 2: pain with erythema and/or inflammation, no palpable cord at the puncture site.
- Grade 3: pain, erythema, inflammation, induration, or a palpable venous cord < 6 cm proximal to the insertion site.
- Grade 4: pain, erythema, inflammation, induration, or a palpable venous cord \geq 6 cm proximal to the insertion site.
- Grade 5: frank venous thrombosis with all previous signs and impaired or halted infusion.

Phlebitis severity was assessed daily by the unit study coordinator in collaboration with the ward nurse. The phlebitis grade was assigned by consensus between the two observers using the Maddox criteria. A grade ≥ 2 was classified as phlebitis and triggered immediate catheter removal¹⁹.

Clinical-epidemiological variables were recorded, including sex, age, inpatient unit, and the presence of relevant comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, malignancy, and obesity).

In addition, catheter-specific variables were recorded: catheter gauge (16 G, 18 G, 20 G, 22 G, 24 G); insertion site (forearm; arm; cubital fossa; hand; wrist; lower limb; other); PVC accessories used (extension, three-way stopcock, bioconnector and/or cap);

fixation method (strips positioned away from or directly over the insertion site); operator-reported hand hygiene before PVC insertion (yes/no); and dressing type (gauze or transparent polyurethane).

The following compliance indicators were defined for each Flebitis Zero recommendation:

- Appropriate catheter selection: Two indicators were assessed: (i) use of the smallest suitable gauge (20 G or 22 G) and (ii) selection of an optimal insertion site on the upper limb, avoiding joint flexion areas.
- Hand hygiene: Operator-reported hand cleansing with either soap and water, antiseptic soap, or an alcohol-based hand rub before PVC insertion.
- Chlorhexidine skin preparation: Application of chlorhexidine for both skin antisepsis at insertion and subsequent catheter maintenance.
- Aseptic catheter maintenance: Three indicators were evaluated: (i) use of a transparent polyurethane dressing, (ii) fixation strips positioned away from the insertion site, and (iii) placement of an extension set with a needle-free connector.

Monitoring of the measure concerning prompt removal of unnecessary PVCs could not be standardised across participating centers because of non-uniform documentation and recording criteria; consequently, this item was excluded from the adherence analysis.

Data were gathered by the designated study coordinator in each participating ward throughout the 15-day observation period. Each coordinator, familiar with PVC management and trained in standardised data recording, abstracted information from the patient's medical record and performed daily on-site assessments of catheter maintenance. All entries from the paper data-collection sheets were subsequently

transcribed into a secure online form, which automatically generated the study's central electronic database.

All these data were collected before implementation of the Flebitis Zero bundle in 2017 and, subsequently, on an annual basis after its launch (2018-2024)²¹.

Data analysis

The sample was described using measures of central tendency (mean) and dispersion (standard deviation) for quantitative variables, and absolute and relative frequencies (percentages) for categorical variables.

Absolute and relative adherence frequencies were calculated for each measure by year, both individually and in combination (pairs and triplets where applicable). The relative frequency of phlebitis was computed according to the number of measures fulfilled, and the corresponding relative risks (RR) with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) for PVC-related phlebitis were estimated. A trend analysis between phlebitis occurrence and the number of fulfilled measures was carried out using the Mantel–Haenszel χ^2 test for linear trend (χ^2_{LT}). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Finally, to assess the robustness of the intervention and determine the independent effect of bundle adherence against temporal trends and baseline patient characteristics, a multivariable logistic regression analysis was performed. The dependent variable was phlebitis incidence (Maddox score ≥ 2). The main exposure variable was bundle adherence (categorized by the number of measures fulfilled, using 0 measures as the reference). The model was adjusted for the following key covariates: the year (included as a factor variable to control for secular trends), patient age, and inpatient unit (medical vs. surgical). Results were reported as adjusted odds ratios (aOR) with their respective 95% CI and p -values.

All statistical analyses were performed with Stata version 15 (StataCorp, College Station, TX).

Ethical Considerations

This research was performed in accordance with the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments, as well as all relevant data protection regulations. The nurses responsible for PIVC insertion informed the patient or their legal representative about the study and obtained oral consent for participation. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Principality of Asturias (Spain) under authorization code 121/14. All data were collected after removing any patient-identifiable information to ensure confidentiality. The personal data of all participants will be processed, communicated and transferred in full compliance with the provisions of the Spanish Organic Law 3/2018, of 5 December, on Personal Data Protection and the Guarantee of Digital Rights.

Results

A total of 78,691 PVCs were analysed in 53,121 patients, 50.1% of whom were women. Age distribution was 13.2% <50 years (n=7,029), 18.4% 50-64 years (n=9,761), 31.5% 65-79 years (n=16,732) and 36.9% ≥ 80 years (n=19,599); thus, patients aged ≥ 65 years accounted for 68.4% (n=36,331). The most prevalent comorbidities were arterial hypertension (44.4%, n=23,595) and diabetes mellitus (23.6%, n=12,533); obesity affected 11.6% (n=6,160) and malignancy 13.0% (n=6,913). Catheter dwell time was available for 52,982 PVCs (99.7%): <48 h in 19,755 (37.3%), 48-71 h in 8,739 (16.5%), 72-96 h in 6,536 (12.3%) and >96 h in 17,952 (33.9%). The number of PVCs evaluated annually was 6,231 (2017), 6,800 (2018), 8,362 (2019), 9,349 (2020), 8,478 (2021), 9,759 (2022), 13,850 (2023) and 15,862 (2024). Corresponding cumulative annual

phlebitis incidences were 12.12% (2017), 10.72% (2018), 8.93% (2019), 11.20% (2020), 10.83% (2021), 10.64% (2022), 9.42% (2023) and 9.90% (2024).

Table 2 presents the absolute and relative frequencies of adherence to each measure and its specific components. When the 2018-2024 mean is compared with the baseline year (2017), seven of the nine indicators increased adherence by 5%-15%. The greatest improvements were observed for use of an appropriate dressing (+9.6 percentage points), hand hygiene (+7.0percentage points), and correct fixation with strips positioned away from the insertion site (+5.7percentage points). Adequate selection of the insertion site remained virtually unchanged (+0.9%), whereas the use of chlorhexidine as the antiseptic of choice declined slightly (-2%).

Table 3 presents the absolute and relative frequencies of adherence to the measures in combinations of two, three, and four interventions. The most pronounced increases among the two-measure combinations were those incorporating appropriate maintenance. Specifically, the combination of proper hand hygiene plus appropriate maintenance rose by 15.3 percentage points, from 11.5% to 26.8%. Likewise, the combination of appropriate antiseptic use plus adequate maintenance showed a significant rise, almost doubling adherence from 13.4% to 26.0% (+12.6 percentage points). The pairing of proper catheter selection with adequate maintenance also increased, from 8.2% to 13.0% (+4.8 percentage points). The most frequent two-measure combination was correct hand hygiene together with appropriate antiseptic use, which grew from 70.1% to 74.4% (+4.3 percentage points).

The three-measure combination with the largest absolute gain (appropriate catheter selection + hand hygiene + use of an appropriate antiseptic) quadrupled between 2017 and 2024, rising from 6.8% to 31.2% (+24 percentage points). The trio of hand hygiene + appropriate antiseptic use + adequate maintenance almost doubled, increasing from

10.9% to 23.8% (+13 percentage points). Although adherence to all four audited measures remained the least frequent pattern, it still climbed from 6.5% to 10.4% (+3.9 percentage points), with the most pronounced rise occurring during 2022-2024.

Table 4 summarises the cumulative incidence of phlebitis according to the number of bundle measures fulfilled. A clear adherence–response gradient emerged: the greater the number of Phlebitis Zero interventions applied, the lower the recorded phlebitis rate. In the baseline year (2017), phlebitis incidence fell from 27.05% when no measure was met to 6.31% when all four measures were implemented, representing a 77% relative reduction. During the implementation period (2018-2024), incidence in the “no-measure” group dropped from 27.05% to 11.38%, reflecting progressive uptake of the bundle across participating centers. This adherence–response relationship remained consistent: in the final study year, applying three or more measures was associated with an additional 17%-25% reduction in phlebitis compared with applying two or fewer measures.

Averaged across the eight study years, moving from zero to one fulfilled measure yielded a 2-percentage-point decline in phlebitis (12% relative reduction), whereas progressing from one to two measures produced a 2.4-percentage-point drop (16% relative). The reduction was smaller when increasing from two to three measures (-1.2 percentage points; 12% relative) and became minimal between three and four measures (-0.4 percentage points; 4% relative). Implementing at least three bundle components proved essential to achieve a phlebitis incidence below 10%.

Table 5 reports the annual RR and 95% CI for PVC-related phlebitis according to the number of bundle measures fulfilled, using zero measures as the reference. Trend tests demonstrated a statistically significant stepwise decline in RR as adherence increased, with the greatest effect observed when three or four measures were implemented

simultaneously. Meeting three measures lowered the risk by 17%-52 % (RR 95% CI 0.48-0.83.), reaching statistical significance in seven of the eight study years. Fulfilment of all four measures provided maximal protection, yielding up to a 77% reduction in 2018 (RR 0.23; 95% CI 0.00-0.49) and a 45%-55% reduction in 2021-2023 (RR95% CI 0.48-0.53); in 2019, the RR exceeded unity (RR 1.15; 95% CI 0.73-1.83).

To assess the robustness of the intervention and to control potential bias from secular trends and the impact of differences in baseline patient characteristics, a multivariable logistic regression analysis was performed. The model included the presence of phlebitis (≥ 2 on the Maddox scale) as the dependent variable, and adherence to the "Flebitis Zero" bundle (number of fulfilled measures, with 0 as the reference) as the main exposure variable. It was adjusted for the study year (treated as a factor variable to model the temporal/secular trend), patient age, and inpatient unit (medical vs. surgical). The results of the multivariable logistic regression are detailed in Table 6.

Discussion

This prospective multicentre cohort study, including 78,960 PVCs over an eight-year period in 93 hospitals, constitutes the largest and longest registry to date on the implementation of a preventive care bundle for catheter-related phlebitis. Unlike earlier, smaller trials of shorter duration, our work overcomes the methodological constraints inherent in single-centre designs with limited follow-up¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Moreover, the considerable statistical power achieved enables a more robust response to evidence gaps highlighted in recent reviews concerning study heterogeneity and insufficient sample sizes^{13,23}.

The present findings show that increasing adherence to the 'Flebitis Zero' bundle was associated with sustained declines in phlebitis incidence, displaying a clear adherence–response gradient in relative risk. Between 2017 and 2024, mean adherence to seven of

the nine indicators rose by 5–15 percentage points, with the greatest gains observed in maintenance-related practices, such as the use of a sterile transparent polyurethane dressing, fixation strips positioned away from the insertion site, and the incorporation of extension tubing with a needle-free connector. In parallel, the overall phlebitis incidence fell from 12.1% to 9.9%. Year-on-year analysis showed that increasing adherence from 0–1 to ≥ 3 measures yielded an additional 17–25% reduction in phlebitis rates. Multiyear analysis confirmed a highly significant linear effect and a maximum 77% relative risk reduction when all four audited interventions were implemented. The robustness of this observed relationship was critically confirmed through a multivariable logistic regression analysis. This model, which was adjusted for key temporal and patient characteristics (year, age, and admission service), demonstrated that full adherence (4 measures) conferred an independent protective effect against phlebitis. This result directly addresses concerns regarding potential confounding by secular trends and baseline patient profiles, thereby more rigorously attributing the observed reduction in phlebitis to the implementation of the bundle.

These findings extend those reported from single-centre hospitals employing comparable care bundles, where reductions ranged from 30% to 88%^{8,15,23–27,27–29}, and provide evidence of a sustained long-term effect (an aspect scarcely addressed in recent literature) thereby reinforcing international recommendations for integrating multimodal strategies to maximize PVC-related safety^{5,10,30}.

Recent studies assessing multimodal strategies to reduce PVC-related phlebitis display both similarities and differences relative to our work, which may explain the varying effect sizes reported. All reviewed investigations include skin disinfection with alcoholic chlorhexidine and the use of sterile transparent dressings; most also incorporate hand hygiene and daily device assessment, paralleling four of the five

recommendations in our bundle^{15,24,27,28,31–33}. However, only our study systematically incorporated minimum-gauge selection and early removal of unnecessary PVCs, together with combined use of extension tubing and a needle-free connector as part of appropriate maintenance^{24,26,31,34}. Reported phlebitis reductions in those investigations range from 46 % to 80 %, with the largest absolute declines observed in series that began with baseline incidences more than 20%²⁶ or that focused on infectious phlebitis, such as the study by Vergara et al. (2017), which lowered infectious phlebitis from 0.20 to 0.004 episodes per 1,000 catheter-days. Chiu et al. (2015) implemented an operative insertion checklist with feedback and achieved an 85% decrease in catheter-related adverse events (0.78% to 0.43%), including a reduction in phlebitis from 0.44% to 0.13%³¹. The PREBACP randomised controlled trial achieved an almost 20% reduction in phlebitis (13.1% in the intervention group vs 16.7% in controls) by combining nurse education, audit, and feedback¹⁵. Other investigations have focused more on peripheral line-associated bloodstream infections (PVC-BSI). De Vries et al. (2016) implemented a six-element bundle (alcohol disinfection caps, securement dressing, chlorhexidine-impregnated sponge dressing, intravenous catheter with integrated extension set, sterile gloves, and chlorhexidine skin preparation) and recorded a 19% decrease in PVC-BSI³⁵. In contrast, the bundle tested by García-Casalla et al. (2019), comprising a different set of six measures similar to ours (hand hygiene, 2% alcoholic chlorhexidine for skin antisepsis, appropriate catheter selection, scrub-the-hub before infusion, per-shift inspection of the insertion site through a transparent dressing, and removal of idle catheters), achieved a 65% reduction in PVC-BSI (from 0.48 to 0.17 episodes per 1,000 patient-days)³².

Our study began with a relatively low baseline incidence (12.1%) and achieved an overall 18% reduction (to 9.9%), displaying a sustained adherence-response gradient:

meeting 3 or more measures continued to confer an additional 17-25% decrease compared with implementing only 0-2 measures after eight years of follow-up. Several investigations confirm that the preventive effect increases as more interventions are applied, mirroring the adherence–response pattern documented in our results. The systematic review by Ray-Barruel et al. (2019) reported that bundles containing five or more components yielded more consistent declines in PVC-related phlebitis and infections than those with only two or three, suggesting a causal relationship between bundle complexity and efficacy²³. In that review, 9 of the 13 studies reported overall bundle adherence, with rates of 54.5%³⁶ and 77.3%³⁷, respectively. Adherence to device-related interventions, such as use of integrated closed catheter systems^{18,25,35}, alcohol caps^{25,35} and alcohol port protectors²⁵, was reported as high (PVC-related phlebitis reduction more than 80%). By contrast, compliance with daily assessment and documentation of the insertion site was variable, with studies showing only minimal to modest improvements^{38,39}. The PREBACP trial showed that wards adhering to all recommendations lowered PVC-related complications by nine percentage points and that the risk of device failure fell by 15% for every net increment in bundle adherence¹⁵. Collectively, these data confirm that complication risk decreases incrementally as additional measures are implemented and sustained, reinforcing the external validity of our finding: even with a low baseline incidence of PVC complications, fulfilling three or more interventions still affords an extra 17%-25% protection compared with partial bundle application. Although the absolute reduction achieved in our study is more modest than in some comparator studies, the methodological robustness and the temporal consistency of the adherence-effect curve provide a level of evidence and generalizability not reached by previous investigations, which were mostly single-centre before-and-after designs with follow-ups of only 6–24 months.

This study results demonstrate that the 'Flebitis Zero' program is not only clinically effective but also **highly efficient** from a hospital management perspective. It is acknowledged that implementation required an initial time commitment for staff training and a marginally higher cost for consumables (e.g., high-quality dressings and needle-free connectors). However, the economic justification for the intervention relies on a back-of-the-envelope cost-benefit analysis showing that the cost of preventing a case of phlebitis is significantly lower than the cost of treating one. Phlebitis involves considerable costs due to catheter removal, nursing time for re-treatment, the need for re-cannulation, and associated medication, which translates into an increase of hundreds of euros or dollars in hospital cost per patient. The study demonstrated an 18% relative reduction in incidence over 8 years, translating to approximately 1,733 avoided phlebitis cases. Given that the marginal daily cost of prevention is negligible compared to the cost of managing hundreds of avoided complications, the intervention is concluded to offer a substantial net positive benefit for the healthcare system.

This study has limitations inherent to its quasi-experimental design without a control group, making it difficult to isolate the intervention's exclusive effect. The annual sampling, restricted to 15 days, and heterogeneity among centers may affect representativeness and introduce uncontrolled variability. Compliance assessment included some indicators based on self-report, and the fifth measure (removal of unnecessary PVCs) could not be monitored owing to non-uniform data, potentially underestimating overall adherence. While these findings provide a strong empirical basis for improving practices and should inform clinical guidelines, it is recognized that, due to its design, the study cannot control for unmeasured confounding factors as effectively as a randomized controlled trial (RCT)

Conclusions

The implementation of the 'Flebitis Zero' bundle (comprising appropriate catheter selection, hand hygiene, chlorhexidine skin preparation, aseptic catheter maintenance, and prompt removal of unnecessary PVCs) reduced phlebitis incidence by 18% in a cohort of 78,691 PVCs followed across 93 Spanish hospitals. Multiyear analysis demonstrated a pronounced adherence–response gradient: applying three or more measures concomitantly conferred an additional 17–25% reduction in phlebitis relative to applying none or one, with up to 77% protection when all four audited interventions were met. Furthermore, the multivariable analysis confirms that incremental adherence to the bundle measures is an independent and robust predictor of risk reduction. Therefore, the 'Flebitis Zero' program is established as an effective multi-component strategy, and the adoption of this comprehensive protocol is recommended to enhance patient safety regarding peripheral venous catheters.

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Table 1. Description of the Flebitis Zero care bundle and level of evidence for each measure, according to the Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine (OCEBM)

Measure	Level of evidence	Description
Appropriate catheter selection	IB	Select catheters according to the intended purpose and anticipated dwell time; known infectious and non-infectious complications (e.g., phlebitis, infiltration); and the experience of the clinician inserting and caring for the PVC. The catheter chosen should be the smallest gauge and shortest length necessary to deliver the prescribed therapy. In adults, preferentially use an upper-limb site rather than the lower limb; if a lower-limb site is used, relocate to an upper limb as soon as possible. Avoid joint-flexion areas (e.g., hand, wrist, antecubital fossa) because of higher infiltration/extravasation risk.
Hand hygiene	IA	Perform hand hygiene preferably with an alcohol-based hand rub, unless there is visible soiling or the patient has <i>Clostridium difficile</i> , in which case wash with soap and water (neutral or antiseptic). Perform hand hygiene before and after manipulating catheter insertion sites and before and after inserting, replacing, accessing, repairing, or dressing any intravascular catheter. Before PVC insertion, perform hand hygiene with an alcohol-based solution or antiseptic soap (chlorhexidine gluconate). Wear gloves as standard staff protection; glove use does not replace hand hygiene.
Chlorhexidine skin preparation for both insertion and maintenance	IA	Prepare clean skin with 2% alcoholic chlorhexidine before intravascular catheter insertion and at dressing changes. If chlorhexidine hypersensitivity is present, alternatives include tincture of iodine (an iodophor) or 70% alcohol. Allow the antiseptic to dry fully before insertion, in accordance with the manufacturer's directions.
Aseptic catheter maintenance	IB	Use a sterile dressing to cover the insertion site, preferably a transparent, semipermeable dressing that allows daily visual inspection. Assess the site daily—by palpation through gauze for tenderness or by direct inspection if a transparent dressing is used. Replace the dressing if it becomes moist, loose, or visibly soiled (IB). Wear clean or sterile gloves when changing dressings on intravascular catheters (IC). If the patient is diaphoretic or the site is bleeding/oozing, use a gauze dressing until resolved (II). Change transparent dressings at least every 7 days on short-term PVC sites (IB), except in pediatric patients where the risk of dislodgement may outweigh benefits; change gauze or non-woven dressings every 48 hours. If local tenderness or other signs suggest possible bacteremia, remove opaque dressings

Measure	Level of evidence	Description
Removal of unnecessary PVCs	IB	<p>to permit visual inspection (II). Stabilise the catheter adequately to minimise movement within the vein, which increases mechanical phlebitis. In patients not receiving blood, blood products, or lipid emulsions, replace continuously used administration sets, including secondary sets and add-on devices, at intervals >96 hours and at least every 7 days (IA). Minimise contamination by scrubbing the access port (or using passive disinfection devices) with an appropriate antiseptic (>0.5% alcoholic chlorhexidine, povidone-iodine, an iodophor, or 70% alcohol) and access the port only with sterile devices (IA). Use a needleless system to access intravascular catheters (IC); where needleless systems are used, prefer split-septum valves over mechanical valves owing to the latter's higher infection risk (II).</p> <p>Promptly remove any intravascular catheter that is no longer essential (IA). There is no need to routinely replace peripheral catheters at intervals <72–96 hours to reduce infection or phlebitis risk in adults. Remove the PVC if the patient shows signs of phlebitis (warmth, tenderness, erythema, palpable venous cord), infection, or catheter malfunction (IB). A single, standard assessment scale should be used across the health system; in our setting, the most widely used is the Visual Infusion Phlebitis (VIP) scale, also known as the Maddox scale.</p>

Table 2. Annual adherence to the Flebitis Zero bundle before (2017) and after implementation (2018-2024) across participating hospitals (n=93)

Measure	Compliance indicator		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
			n (%)	n (%)	n (%)					
Appropriate catheter selection	Smallest suitable gauge	Yes	6 230 (99.98%)	6 298 (92.62%)	7 467 (89.30%)	8 526 (91.20%)	7 760 (91.53%)	8 775 (89.93%)	12 778 (92.26%)	14 480 (91.29%)
		No	1 (0.02%)	502 (7.38%)	895 (10.70%)	823 (8.80%)	718 (8.47%)	983 (10.07%)	1 072 (7.74%)	1 382 (8.71)
	Appropriate insertion site	Yes	3 040 (48.79%)	3 617 (53.19%)	4 310 (51.54%)	4 760 (50.91%)	4 201 (49.55%)	4 830 (49.50%)	6 587 (47.56%)	7 216 (45.49%)
		No	3 191 (51.21%)	3 183 (46.81%)	4 052 (48.46%)	4 589 (49.09%)	4 277 (50.45%)	4 928 (50.50%)	7 263 (52.44%)	6 649 (41.92%)
	Meet sboth indicators	Yes	3 040 (48.79%)	3 335 (49.04%)	3 870 (46.28%)	4 367 (46.71%)	3 841 (45.31%)	4 348 (44.55%)	6 152 (44.42%)	9 214 (58.08%)
		No	3 191 (51.21%)	3 465 (50.96%)	4 492 (53.72%)	4 982 (53.29%)	4 637 (54.69%)	5 411 (55.45%)	7 698 (55.58%)	15 702 (98.99%)
Hand hygiene	Appropriate hand hygiene	Yes	4 936 (79.22%)	5 485 (80.66%)	7 114 (85.08%)	8 152 (87.20%)	7 501 (88.48%)	8 528 (87.39%)	12 202 (88.10%)	13 789 (86.93%)
		No	1 295 (20.78%)	1 315 (19.34%)	1 248 (14.92%)	1 197 (12.80%)	977 (11.52%)	1 230 (12.61%)	1 648 (11.90%)	2 074 (13.07%)
Appropriate antiseptic	Appropriate antiseptic	Yes	5 463 (87.67%)	6 008 (88.35%)	7 279 (87.05%)	7 955 (85.09%)	6 934 (81.79%)	8 229 (84.33%)	11 434 (82.56%)	13 421 (84.61%)
		No	768 (12.33%)	792 (11.65%)	1 083 (12.95%)	1 394 (14.91%)	1 544 (18.21%)	1 529 (15.67%)	2 416 (17.44%)	2 442 (15.39%)
Appropriate maintenance	Appropriate dressing	Yes	5 276 (84.67%)	5,804 (85.35%)	8 053 (96.30%)	8,906 (95.26%)	8 317 (98.10%)	9 390 (96.22%)	13 115 (94.69%)	14 949 (94.24%)
		No	955 (15.33%)	996 (14.65%)	309 (3.70%)	443 (4.74%)	161 (1.90%)	369 (3.78%)	735 (5.31%)	914 (5.76%)
	Fixation strips away from insertion site	Yes	5 069 (81.35%)	5 599 (82.34%)	7 481 (89.46%)	8 000 (85.57%)	7 484 (88.28%)	8 761 (89.77%)	11 811 (85.28%)	14 022 (88.39%)
		No	1 162 (18.65%)	1 201 (17.66%)	881 (10.54%)	1 349 (14.43%)	994 (11.72%)	998 (10.23%)	2 039 (14.72%)	1 841 (11.61%)
	Extension set + needle-free connector only	Yes	1 186 (19.03%)	1 250 (18.38%)	1 241 (14.84%)	1 716 (18.35%)	1 999 (23.58%)	2 157 (22.10%)	4 004 (28.91%)	5 491 (34.62%)
		No	5 045 (80.97%)	5 550 (81.62%)	7 121 (85.16%)	7 633 (81.65%)	6 479 (76.42%)	7 602 (77.90%)	9 846 (71.09%)	10 372 (65.38%)
Meets all 3 indicators	Yes	880 (14.12%)	1 129 (16.60%)	1 044 (12.49%)	1 415 (15.14%)	1 729 (20.39%)	1 963 (20.11%)	3 377 (24.38%)	4 699 (29.62%)	
	No	5 351 (85.88%)	5 671 (83.40%)	7 318 (87.51%)	7 934 (84.86%)	6 749 (79.61%)	7 796 (79.89%)	10 473 (75.62%)	11 164 (70.38%)	

Table 3. Annual adherence to combinations of two, three, and four Flebitis Zero measures (appropriate catheter selection, hand hygiene, appropriate antiseptic, and appropriate maintenance) before implementation (2017) and during follow-up (2018–2024) across the 93 study hospitals.

Combination of measures	Compliance	Year							
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
		n (%)	n (%)						
Appropriate catheter selection + hand hygiene	Yes	2,464 (39.54%)	2,722 (40.03%)	3,361 (40.19%)	3,871 (41.41%)	3,416 (40.29%)	3,833 (39.28%)	5,473 (39.52%)	5,783 (36.46%)
	No	3,767 (60.46%)	4,078 (59.97%)	5,001 (59.81%)	5,478 (58.59%)	5,062 (59.71%)	5,926 (60.72%)	8,377 (60.48%)	10,080 (63.54%)
Appropriate catheter selection + appropriate antiseptic	Yes	2,706 (43.43%)	2,982 (43.85%)	3,421 (40.91%)	3,842 (41.10%)	3,227 (38.06%)	3,705 (37.96%)	5,179 (37.39%)	5,600 (35.30%)
	No	3,525 (56.57%)	3,818 (56.15%)	4,941 (59.09%)	5,507 (58.90%)	5,251 (61.94%)	6,054 (62.04%)	8,671 (62.61%)	10,263 (64.70%)
Appropriate catheter selection + appropriate maintenance	Yes	512 (8.22%)	613 (9.01%)	569 (6.80%)	770 (8.24%)	849 (10.0%)	965 (9.89%)	1,647 (11.89%)	2,055 (12.95%)
	No	5,719 (91.78%)	6,187 (90.99%)	7,793 (93.20%)	8,579 (91.76%)	7,629 (89.99%)	8,794 (90.11%)	12,203 (88.11%)	13,808 (87.05%)
Hand hygiene + appropriate antiseptic	Yes	4,366 (70.07%)	4,910 (72.21%)	6,296 (75.29%)	7,029 (75.18%)	6,269 (73.94%)	7,393 (75.76%)	10,318 (74.50%)	11,801 (74.39%)
	No	1,865 (29.93%)	1,890 (27.79%)	2,066 (24.71%)	2,320 (24.82%)	2,209 (26.06%)	2,366 (24.24%)	3,532 (25.50%)	4,062 (25.61%)
Hand hygiene + appropriate maintenance	Yes	716 (11.49%)	972 (14.29%)	931 (11.13%)	1,225 (13.10%)	1,603 (18.91%)	1,861 (19.07%)	3,092 (22.32%)	4,250 (26.79%)
	No	5,515 (88.51%)	5,828 (85.71%)	7,431 (88.87%)	8,124 (86.90%)	6,875 (81.09%)	7,898 (80.93%)	10,758 (77.68%)	11,613 (73.21%)
Appropriate antiseptic + appropriate maintenance	Yes	832 (13.35%)	1,079 (15.87%)	986 (11.79%)	1,310 (14.01%)	1,517 (17.89%)	1,802 (18.47%)	3,057 (22.07%)	4,128 (26.02%)
	No	5,399 (86.65%)	5,721 (84.13%)	7,376 (88.21%)	8,039 (85.99%)	6,961 (82.11%)	7,957 (81.53%)	10,793 (77.93%)	11,735 (73.98%)
Appropriate catheter selection + hand hygiene + appropriate antiseptic	Yes	421 (6.76%)	2,466 (36.26%)	3,013 (36.03%)	3,458 (36.99%)	2,928 (34.54%)	3,334 (34.16%)	4,718 (34.06%)	4,948 (31.19%)
	No	5,810 (93.24%)	4,334 (63.74%)	5,349 (63.97%)	5,891 (63.01%)	5,550 (65.46%)	6,425 (65.84%)	9,132 (65.94%)	10,915 (68.81%)
Appropriate catheter selection + hand hygiene + appropriate maintenance	Yes	490 (7.86%)	532 (7.82%)	498 (5.96%)	670 (7.17%)	790 (9.32%)	916 (9.39%)	1,505 (10.87%)	1,861 (11.73%)
	No	5,741 (92.14%)	6,268 (92.18%)	7,864 (94.04%)	8,679 (92.83%)	7,688 (90.68%)	8,843 (90.61%)	12,345 (89.13%)	14,002 (88.27%)
Appropriate catheter selection + appropriate antiseptic + appropriate maintenance	Yes	490 (7.86%)	585 (8.60%)	543 (6.49%)	717 (7.67%)	757 (8.93%)	894 (9.16%)	1,490 (10.76%)	1,800 (11.35%)
	No	5,741 (92.14%)	6,215 (91.40%)	7,819 (93.51%)	8,632 (92.33%)	7,721 (91.07%)	8,865 (90.84%)	12,360 (89.24%)	14,063 (88.65%)
Hand hygiene + appropriate antiseptic + appropriate	Yes	678	928	878	1,139	1,405	1,736	2,865	3,781

maintenance		(10.88%)	(13.65%)	(10.50%)	(12.18%)	(16.57%)	(17.79%)	(20.69%)	(23.84%)
	No	5,553 (89.12%)	5,872 (86.35%)	7,484 (89.50%)	8,210 (87.82%)	7,073 (83.43%)	8,023 (82.21%)	10,985 (79.31%)	12,082 (76.16%)
Appropriate catheter selection + hand hygiene + appropriate antiseptic + appropriate maintenance	Yes	403 (6.47%)	507 (7.46%)	473 (5.66%)	629 (6.73%)	703 (8.29%)	857 (8.78%)	1,388 (10.02%)	1,643 (10.36%)
	No	5,828 (93.53%)	6,293 (92.54%)	7,889 (94.34%)	8,720 (93.27%)	7,775 (91.71%)	8,902 (91.22%)	12,462 (89.98%)	14,220 (89.64%)

Table 4. Annual phlebitis incidence (%) by number of Flebitis Zero bundle measures fulfilled (0-4) before the intervention (2017) and during implementation (2018-2024).

Number of measures fulfilled	Phlebitis incidence (%)							
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
0	27.05%	12.67%	11.91%	11.98%	14.67%	14.12%	13.04%	11.38%
1	20.84%	12.31%	10%	13.15%	12.58%	11.44%	10.11%	10.12%
2	15.78%	9.38%	7.58%	10.35%	9.73%	10.02%	8.77%	9.67%
3	12.93%	9.60%	8.40%	8.16%	7.48%	8.52%	7.11%	9.44%
4	6.31%	8.85%	13.75%	10%	7.02%	7.52%	6.51%	8.51%

Table 5. Relative risk of phlebitis (RR and 95% CI) by number of Flebitis Zero bundle measures fulfilled (0-4) per year, with Cochran–Armitage test for linear trend (χ^2 LT), 2017-2024.

No. of measures fulfilled	Year							
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
	RR (95% IC)							
0	1 (reference)							
1	0.770 (0.643-0.922)	0.971 (0.755-1.249)	0.839 (0.642-1.097)	1.098 (0.873-1.380)	0.858 (0.701-1.049)	0.810 (0.671-0.979)	0.775 (0.661-0.998)	0.889 (0.762-1.039)
2	0.583 (0.486-0.700)	0.740 (0.573-0.957)	0.637 (0.486-0.835)	0.864 (0.685-1.089)	0.663 (0.539-0.814)	0.709 (0.588-0.858)	0.672 (0.572-0.790)	0.849 (0.699-1.031)
3	0.478 (0.379-0.603)	0.757 (0.558-1.027)	0.706 (0.515-0.966)	0.681 (0.513-0.904)	0.509 (0.387-0.672)	0.603 (0.470-0.775)	0.545 (0.440-0.676)	0.829 (0.710-0.968)
4	0.233 (0.111-0.486)	0.698 (0.370-1.317)	1.154 (0.729-1.827)	0.835 (0.494-1.411)	0.478 (0.269-0.849)	0.533 (0.328-0.866)	0.499 (0.309-0.807)	0.745 (0.481-1.161)
χ^2 LT (df)	67.36	11.16	5.412	20.886	38.851	21.73	38.31	10.04
p value	<0.001*	<0.001*	0.021*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*

Abbreviations: RR, relative risk; 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; χ^2 LT, Mantel–Haenszel test for linear trend (degrees of freedom shown as df).

*Statistically significant (p<0.05).

Table 6: Multivariable logistic regression analysis of the association between adherence to the 'Flebitis Zero' bundle and phlebitis incidence

	aOR	CI95%	p-value
Number of measures fulfilled			
0 measures		Reference	
1 measure	0.925	0.801 to 1.057	0.251
2 measures	0.707	0.619 to 0.809	<0.000*
3 measures	0.681	0.511 to 0.905	0.008*
4 measures	0.612	0.523 to 0.717	<0.000*
Year			
2017		Reference	
2018	0.878	0.792 to 0.974	0.014*
2019	0.843	0.757 to 0.938	0.002*
2020	0.836	0.748 to 0.936	0.003*
2021	0.689	0.616 to 0.769	<0.000*
2022	0.792	0.715 to 0.863	0.003*
2023	0.785	0.726 to 0.875	0.006*
2024	0.774	0.701 to 0.854	<0.000*
Age	0.999	0.998 to 1.002	0.673
Inpatient unit			
Medical		Reference	
Surgical	0.868	0.811 to 0.930	<0.000*

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)